

DATA PEER REVIEW GUIDELINES

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Note to the reader:

We'd love to hear your thoughts! If you have any feedback on this template, want to share your experience, or have ideas for improvement, please go to this [Google Doc](#).

If you would like to use this template, please access the [editable version](#) of the guidelines.

As part of a pilot project on data and software peer review at the TU Delft Library, we developed this template for peer reviewing datasets.¹ In creating the template, we referred to existing data peer review guidelines at journals that publish data papers, as well as existing practices in research teams. The template distinguishes between 'technical' and 'scientific' checks. Technical checks are concerned with the completeness and FAIRness of a dataset, for instance whether there is a README file, an adequate description, metadata, license, and so on. The additional scientific checks look at the quality of data and methodology of data collection, and whether supporting experiments are adequately described, research questions addressed. This would require some accompanying documentation to review, such as a short data paper or journal article. Such a review would be best suited, as with other data peer review practices, at a journal where datasets and accompanying data papers (or articles) are published. However, the template is free to use and adapt as best suited to context.

The template is aimed at a data reviewer who may be from a trusted repository, a journal, or a university/research institution. We do not assume the data is always related to an article nor that the reviewer has access to such an article (except where specified).

The following suggestions are based on the distinction between raw, processed and finalized data; where:

- Raw data correspond to the data obtained directly from an instrument; a (simulation) code; the raw answers from a questionnaire; etc.
- Processed data correspond to any modification (in shape or content) made to the raw data following a given methodology for the purpose of doing research. That is: cleaned up raw data; anonymized data; and so on.
- Finalized data correspond to the tabular data and images corresponding to the tables and the plots presented in an article, thesis, and so on.

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'Technical' checks of the dataset (applicable to repositories, institutions, journals)

General assessment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Is the dataset findable: data registered/indexed with a unique persistent identifier <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ <i>Are there any related identifiers to the dataset (like sub datasets or whether data of other groups has been reused)</i> • Is the dataset cited in the paper (if associated with a research paper/publication)? • Is there a contact address listed for further queries? • Are all contributors appropriately listed/acknowledged?
Metadata	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Is the title of the dataset (as stated in citation metadata of the repository and the supporting documentation presented in the dataset) understandable and consistent with what the dataset contains? <p>Citation metadata (of the repository where the data is being published):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Is the information of all authors correct? • Is the description of the dataset clear and consistent as to what the dataset contains? • This information should be in the description of the dataset in both, the citation metadata and the supporting documentation (README). In the citation metadata this information should be summarized, while in the supporting documentation it should be provided in more detail. Based on whether the data is raw, processed or finalised; <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ <i>If it is raw data: is there a clear explanation of how it was obtained (such as instruments, facilities, dates, software).?</i> ▪ <i>If it is processed data: is there information about the raw data from which the processed data is derived? Is there information about the processing steps applied to the raw data (including software, methodology, caveats)?</i> ▪ <i>If it is finalized data: is there information about the raw and processed data from which the finalized data is derived?</i> • Are there any articles related to the dataset? If yes, are they included in the citation metadata of the dataset? • Are there any other references mentioned in the dataset that should also be included in the citation metadata? Other references can include code repositories, standard protocols, funding agencies.
Files	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Are the files in open or standard formats? • Is there a README file? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ <i>Does it contain information about how the data was collected/processed?</i> ▪ <i>Does it contain information about naming of variables, units and any extra disciplinary metadata?</i> ▪ <i>Does it contain a description of the dataset structure?</i> ▪ <i>Does it contain a description of caveats, errors and assumptions considered while collecting/processing the data?</i> ▪ <i>Are all references properly indicated?</i> ▪ <i>Is the methodology well described?</i> ▪ Are all the files described? • Is there extra supporting documentation (such as logs, manuals)? • Are there extra supporting discipline-specific metadata (such as XML files)? • Can the files be opened without problems? Is there sufficient information about what the files contain? • Do the files contain errors/missing values not explained in the supporting documentation?
License	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Is there a single license or are there files licensed under different licenses? If it is the latter, how are these specified? • Is the license consistent with the related data and the concept of Open Science?

'Scientific' checks of the dataset (additional checks, applicable for journals or where additional documentation [like a paper/preprint or other description] is also available)

Dataset	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Is the dataset appropriate for answering the research questions posed in the accompanying publication? (if there is an accompanying publication)• Is the dataset complete? (is validation information available)• Is the dataset error/missing-values free?
Methodology	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Is the methodology for data collection properly described (for instance, how samples were collected or how interviews were conducted)?• Are the methodology and study design replicable (for instance, are all variables defined, and is there enough detail so that others could reproduce or follow the steps taken)?• Are the equipment and supporting experiments described?